

Scheme 1

TABLE 1					
Compd. no.	X ₁	X ₂	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Ia	H	H	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	209-10	50
Ib	Br	H	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	175-77	90
Ic	Br	Br	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₂ O ₅ Br ₂	162-63	60
Id	I	H	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ I	196-97	90

10,12-Substituted [1,4]-benzoxazino [3,4]-quinazolin-8-ones (IIa-d): Benzoxazine (Ia-d, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and Raney nickel (0.5 g) was placed into it. Hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was then carefully added at room temperature and after the evolution of hydrogen ceased the reaction mixture was allowed to reflux on a water bath for 3 h. It was then acidified with hot 5 N hydrochloric acid and filtered hot. Filtrate on cooling yielded the crude product which was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2). Absence of the bands

TABLE 2					
Compd. no.	X ₁	X ₂	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
IIa	H	H	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	155-56	60
IIb	Br	H	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ Br	166-67	65
IIc	Br	Br	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₂ O ₅ Br ₂	164-65	55
IId	I	H	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ I	165-66	65

in ir (KBr) at 1360 and 1525 cm⁻¹ due to the aromatic nitro group present in its precursor indicated that the reduction of nitro group was complete

and also the absence of 3300-3400 cm⁻¹ band confirmed that the amino group formed during this reduction had reacted intramolecularly with benzoxazine carbonyl group to form the desired product.

Biological screening: The method of Kamboj *et al.*⁷ was adopted to evaluate the anti-implantation activity. Compounds were found to have an activity range between 12.5-37.5% only at a dose level of 25 mg/kg body weight of the animal.

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Azomethines and Thiazolidinones Derived from 2-Phenyl-3-(p-aminodiphenyl)-4-quinazolones

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QUINAZOLONES¹⁻⁵ and azomethines/Schiff's^{6,7} bases are reported to exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities. Thiazolidinones also possess a variety of pharmacological properties, viz. amoebicidal⁸, hypnotic⁹, anticonvulsant¹⁰, fungicidal¹¹ and antibacterial¹². In view of these observations we thought it of interest to synthesise and investigate the azomethines having a quinazolone nucleus and compounds containing the quinazolone and thiazolidinone moieties in a single molecular framework as possible antibacterial agents.

2-Phenyl-3-(p-aminodiphenyl)-4-quinazolone¹³ (I) was refluxed with different arylaldehydes in absolute alcohol in presence of few drops of acetic acid to

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL DATA OF 2-PHENYL-3-(*p*-ARYLIDENEAMINODIPHENYL)-4-QUINAZOLONE (II)

Sl. no.	M.p. °C	Antibacterial activity*					
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumilis</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. branchiseptica</i>	<i>S. lutea</i>	
IIa	2-Furyl	>250	++	+++	+++	+	+++
IIb	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	239	++	+++	+++	++	++++
IIc	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	232	++	+++	+++	+	++++
IId	2-Hydroxyphenyl	234	++	+++	+++	+	+++
IIe	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	235	++	+++	+++	+	++++
IIf	4-Nitrophenyl	215	++	+++	+++	+	++++
IIg	Phenyl	230	++	+++	+++	++	++++
IIh	4-Hydroxyphenyl	228	++	+++	+++	++	++++

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

* Zone size: + = 6-8 mm, ++ = 9-16 mm, +++ = 17-25 mm, ++++ = >26 mm.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL DATA OF 2-PHENYL-3-*p*(2-ARYL-4-OXO-THIAZOLIN-3-YL)-DIPHENYL-4-QUINAZOLONE (III)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Antibacterial activity*				
			<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pumilis</i>	<i>S. subtilis</i>	<i>B. branchiseptica</i>	<i>S. lutea</i>
IIIa	2-Furyl	>250	++	++++	+++	-	+++
IIIb	4- <i>N,N</i> -Diethylphenyl	242	++	++++	+++	-	++++
IIIc	4- <i>N,N</i> -Dimethylphenyl	218	++	+++	+++	-	+++
IIId	2-Hydroxyphenyl	244	++	+++	+++	-	+++
IIIe	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	266	++	+++	+++	-	++++
IIIf	4-Nitrophenyl	270	++	+++	+++	-	++++
IIIg	Phenyl	225	++	+++	+++	-	++++
IIIh	4-Hydroxyphenyl	201	++	++++	+++	-	++++

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

* Zone size: - = No inhibition, + = 6-8 mm, ++ = 9-16 mm, +++ = 17-25 mm, ++++ = >26 mm.

get the desired 2-phenyl-3-(*p*-arylideneaminodiphenyl)-4-quinazolones (II), which were reacted with thioglycolic acid to furnish 2-phenyl-3-*p*(2-aryl-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl)diphenyl-4-quinazolones (III). Structure of compounds II and III were characterized by their elemental analyses and ir spectra. Com-

ound II gave peaks at 1640 ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and 1680-1670 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}=\text{CH}$ -azomethine linkage), whereas compound III gave peaks at 1650-1585 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1600-1610 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ aromatic), 1420-1520 ($\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretching), 1250-1350 ($\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{C}$) and 745-820 cm^{-1} (substituted benzene).

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid bath in open capillary. Tlc was done on silica gel plates.

2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-aminodiphenyl)-4-quinazolone (I) : It was obtained in good yield by the reported method¹⁸.

2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-arylideneaminodiphenyl)-4-quinazolone (II) : A mixture of I (0.01 mol), arylaldehyde (0.01 mol), ethanol (25 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 5-6 h. The resulting mixture was cooled and poured over crushed ice. The coloured solid product obtained was washed several

times with water and then recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3-*p*(2-aryl-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl)diphenyl-4-quinazolone (III) : Thioglycolic acid (0.015 mol)

was added to a well stirred solution of II (0.05 mol) in dry benzene/dioxane (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The excess solvent was removed and the solid mass washed with aqueous sodium carbonate solution (10%) and finally recrystallised from petroleum ether or benzene. The melting points and other data of the compounds are recorded in Table 2.

Antibacterial screening: Agar plate diffusion technique¹⁴ was employed for the determination of antibacterial activity of the synthesised compounds of type II and III against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus branchi-septice*, and *Sarcina lutea*. The results are given in Table 1 and 2.

The antibacterial activity of both the series seems to be sporadic with no apparent pattern and thus making it difficult to correlate with structural requirements.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Evaluation of 1-(Phenyl/methylcarbamoyloxyphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone, A New Class of Carbamates†

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A number of 1-(hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone and their *N*-methyl and *N*-phenyl carbamates have been synthesised and evaluated for their antimicrobial activities against a number of bacteria and fungi.

The biological properties associated with *N*-methyl, *N,N*-dimethyl and *N*-phenyl carbamic esters of various alcohols and phenols have been reported¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our interest towards the synthesis of potential antimicrobial agents^{5,6}, we hereby report the synthesis of the title carbamates according to the sequence of reaction outlined in Chart 1 with a view to study their antimicrobial efficacy. The choice of imidazolone derivatives arose because their number of analogues have been shown to exhibit diverse types of biological activities including antibacterial properties.

Chart 1

Various 2-methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolone (1-5), obtained by the condensation of acetyl/benzoylglycine with several aryl aldehydes, on reaction with various aminophenols in pyridine, furnished 1-(hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl/

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